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4 **Physiological responses and lactational performances of late-lactation dairy**
5 **goats under heat stress conditions**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Eight Murciano-Granadina dairy goats in late lactation were exposed to different ambient
15 conditions, using metabolic cages in a climatic chamber. Experimental design was a crossover
16 (2 periods of 35 d and 4 goats each), and conditions were: 1) thermal neutral (TN, 15 to 20°C
17 day-night), and 2) heat stress (HS, 12-h day at 37°C and 12-h night at 30.5°C). Humidity was
18 maintained at 40% and light-dark was constant (12-12 h). Forage:concentrate ratio was
19 adjusted daily for maintaining similar value in TN and HS goats (70:30). Water was freely
20 available at ambient temperature. Rectal temperature and respiratory rate (0800, 1200 and
21 1700 h) and milk yield were recorded daily, whereas milk composition, nonesterified fatty
22 acids (NEFA) and haptoglobin in blood were analyzed weekly. At d 25, additional blood
23 samples were taken for analysis of metabolites and indicators of the acid-base balance.
24 Digestibility coefficients and N balance were determined (d 31 to 35) and body weight was
25 recorded (d 35). Compared to TN goats, HS goats experienced greater rectal temperature
26 (+0.58 °C), respiratory rate (+48 breaths/min), water intake (+77%) and water evaporation
27 (+207%). Intake of HS goats rapidly declined until d 7 (-40%), partially recovered from d 7
28 to 19, and steadied thereafter (-14%). No changes in digestibility or N balance were detected.
29 Blood NEFA and haptoglobin peaked at d 7 in HS goats but did not vary thereafter. Although
30 milk yield did not vary by treatment, milk of HS goats contained -12.5% protein and -11.5%
31 casein than TN goats. Panting reduced concentration and pressure of CO₂ in blood of HS
32 goats, but they were able to maintain their blood pH similar to TN group by lowering HCO₃⁻
33 and increasing Cl⁻ concentrations in blood. In conclusion, heat-stressed dairy goats showed
34 dramatic physiological changes during the first week of treatment and partially recovered
35 thereafter. They were able to maintain milk yield by losing body mass, but milk protein
36 content and protein yield were depressed. Further research is needed to assess the response of
37 dairy goats to heat stress at earlier stages of lactation.

38 **Key words:** heat stress, lactation, digestibility, dairy goat

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INTRODUCTION

41 Heat stress (**HS**) decreases milk production of dairy animals, and a half of this reduction in
42 milk yield is due to reduced DMI (Rhoads et al., 2009). The other half of milk yield losses
43 could be explained by the increase in maintenance requirements (NRC, 2007), decreasing
44 secretion of growth hormone (Mitra et al., 1972), lowering blood flow to the udder (Lough et
45 al., 1990), down-regulating milk protein genes and up-regulating apoptosis genes in the
46 mammary gland (Collier et al., 2006). Cows under HS had greater levels of insulin with
47 improved insulin sensitivity and lacked the ability of fat mobilization from adipose tissue to
48 face the decreased DMI (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013). The reduction in dairy farm profit
49 associated with HS when the temperature-humidity index (**THI**) is extremely high is not only
50 a result of decreased milk yield, but also includes impaired milk quality, reproduction
51 problems, increased health care costs, and even animal death.

52 Despite the large number of studies carried out in dairy cows, little is known about the
53 effects of HS in dairy goats. Goats are considered more tolerant to high THI values compared
54 to dairy cows because of their metabolic size and high water conservation capacity
55 (Silanikove, 2000). When environmental temperatures increased from 20 to 40°C, respiration
56 rate increased from 30 to over 200 breaths/min in East African goats (Maloiy and Taylor,
57 1971) and domestic Swedish goats (Olsson et al., 1995), indicating that water evaporation by
58 respiration plays an important role in heat dissipation in goats.

59 Lactating Saanen goats exposed to moderate or severe HS for 4 d (THI, 81 or 89) lost milk
60 yield by 3 or 13%, respectively (Sano et al., 1985). Brown et al. (1988) reported that the
61 exposure of dairy goats to moderate HS conditions for 5 wk (34°C and 25% humidity; THI =

62 79) depressed milk yield in Alpine but not in Nubian goats, indicating that the response to HS
63 varies according to breed.

64 The objective of the current study was to measure the physiological, lactational, and
65 nutritional responses to extreme heat stress conditions in Spanish Murciano-Granadina dairy
66 goats at late lactation. Moreover, blood acid-base status and stress indicators were also
67 evaluated. No information is available on the effects of heat stress on this dairy breed, which
68 is widely spread in the Mediterranean area.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

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Animal and Management Conditions

72
73 Animal care conditions and management practices agreed with the procedures stated by the
74 Ethical Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
75 Barcelona (CEEAH reference 09/771) and the codes of recommendations for the welfare of
76 livestock of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment of Spain.

77 Eight open multiparous Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (43.5 ± 2.6 kg BW) with healthy
78 and symmetrical udders, from the herd of the experimental farm of the Universitat Autònoma
79 de Barcelona were blocked in 2 balanced groups and used at late lactation (194 ± 3 DIM; 1.53
80 ± 0.04 L/d).

81 The experimental design was a crossover with 2 treatments in 2 periods, lasting 35 d, and 4
82 goats each. Goats were switched to the opposite treatment in the second period. Climatic
83 conditions were: 1) thermal neutral (TN; 15 to 20°C and 45%; THI = 59 to 65), and 2) heat
84 stress (HS; 12-h day at 37°C and 40%; THI = 85; and 12-h night at 30.5°C and 40%; THI =
85 77). Order of treatments on each goat was recorded and taken into account in the statistical
86 analyses. The THI values were calculated according to NRC (1971) as follows:

87 $THI = (1.8 \times T_{db} + 32) - [(0.55 - 0.0055 \times RH) \times (1.8 \times T_{db} - 26.8)]$, where T_{db} is the dry
88 bulb temperature ($^{\circ}C$) and RH is the relative humidity (%).

89 Throughout the experiment, (mid-January to mid-April), the TN goats were kept indoors
90 and the temperature was maintained at 15 to 20 $^{\circ}C$ with the help of electric heater equipped
91 with a thermostat (3.5 kW; General Electric, Barcelona, Spain). Temperature and relative
92 humidity averaged $16.7 \pm 0.3^{\circ}C$ and $45 \pm 5\%$ ($THI = 61$) for the TN goats. The HS goats were
93 kept in a 4 \times 6 \times 2.3 m climatic chamber (Euroshield, ETS Lindgren-Euroshield Oy, Eura,
94 Finland) provided with a temperature and humidity controlling system (CAREL Controls
95 Ibérica, S.L., Barcelona, Spain). A continuous 90 m³/h air turnover was maintained
96 throughout the experiment.

97 Goats had a 4-wk pre-experimental period under TN conditions for the adaptation to the
98 diet and to metabolic cages. When goats were switched from TN to HS conditions, a
99 transition period of 2 d was allowed (1 d at 25 $^{\circ}C$ and 1 d at 30 $^{\circ}C$), but no transition was
100 applied for the change from HS to TN. Photoperiod was maintained constant at 12-12 h light-
101 dark (0900 to 2100 h) and data of environmental temperature and humidity were recorded
102 every 10 min by using 2 data loggers (Opus 10, Lufft, Fellbach, Germany).

103 Daily ration of the goats consisted of (as fed) dehydrated fescue hay ad libitum (20% daily
104 refusal), 0.65 kg alfalfa pellets, and 0.8 kg of concentrate mixture (corn, 30%; barley, 25.8%;
105 soybean meal, 25%; sunflower meal, 8.5%; fatty acid sodium salts, 5%; dicalcium phosphate,
106 2.5%; calcium carbonate, 2%; sodium chloride, 1%; and vitamins A, E, and D3; as fed).
107 Mineralized salt blocks were freely available in each metabolic cage (Composition: Na,
108 36.74%; Ca, 0.32; Mg, 1.09%; Zn, 5 g/kg; Mn, 1.5 g/kg; S, 912 mg/kg; Fe, 304 mg/kg; I, 75
109 mg/kg; Co, 50 mg/kg; Se, 25 mg/kg; Ovi bloc, Sal Cupido, Terrasa, Spain). The concentrate
110 mixture was offered in 2 daily portions at 0900 and 1600 h. Changes in the forage intake of
111 the HS goats were taken into account throughout the experiment and the amount of

112 concentrate offered was daily modified to maintain a constant and similar forage:concentrate
113 ratio to that of the TN goats. Clean water was permanently available at ambient temperature,
114 according to treatment.

115 Goats were milked once daily (0800 h) with a portable milking machine (Westfalia-
116 Separator Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) set at 42 kPa, 90 pulses/min, and 66% pulsation ratio,
117 provided of recording jars (2 L \pm 5%). Milking routine included cluster attachment without
118 udder preparation or teat cleaning, machine milking, machine stripping before cluster
119 removal, and teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-ioshield, Ecolab Hispano-Portuguesa,
120 Barcelona, Spain).

121

122 *Sample Collection, Analyses, and Measurements*

123 ***Body Temperature and Respiration Rate.*** Rectal temperatures and respiration rates were
124 recorded at 0800, 1200, and 1700 h. Rectal temperature was measured by a digital clinical
125 thermometer (Model ICO Technology "mini color", Barcelona, Spain; range, 32 to 43.9°C;
126 accuracy, \pm 0.1°C), whereas number of inhalations and exhalations during 60 s indicated the
127 respiration rate.

128 ***Feed Intake and Water Consumption.*** Feed intake and water consumption (accuracy, \pm 20
129 g) were recorded daily throughout the experiment. Trays with saw dust were put below the
130 drinking troughs and weighted twice daily to take into account water wastes. Feed samples
131 were collected before the beginning of each experimental period and were ground through a 1
132 mm stainless steel screen, and then analyzed for DM, ADF, NDF, and ash according to
133 analytical standard methods (AOAC, 2003). The Dumas method (AOAC, 2003) with a Leco
134 analyzer (Leco Corporation, St. Joseph, MI) was used for N determinations and CP was
135 calculated as percentage of N \times 6.25. The chemical composition and nutritive value of ration
136 ingredients are shown in Table 1.

137 ***Milk Yield and Milk Composition.*** Milk yield of individual goats was recorded daily
138 throughout the experiment and milk composition was evaluated weekly. A milk sample of
139 approximately 100 mL was collected and preserved with an antimicrobial tablet (Bronopol,
140 Broad Spectrum Microtabs II, D&F Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) at 4°C until
141 analysis. Milk samples were analyzed with a near-infrared spectrometer (Foss NIRSystems
142 5000, Foss, Hillerød, Denmark) for contents of TS, fat, total protein ($N \times 6.38$), true protein,
143 and CN. Whey protein was calculated by the difference between true protein and CN, and
144 NPN was calculated by the difference between total protein and true protein.

145 ***Blood Measures.*** Blood samples were taken weekly from the jugular vein into 10 mL
146 plastic lavender-vacutainers with spray-coated K₂-EDTA (BD Diagnostics, Franklin Lakes,
147 NJ) before the morning feeding. Plasma was obtained by centrifugation of whole blood for 15
148 min at 1500 × g, and stored at -20°C for the NEFA and haptoglobin analyses. The NEFA
149 were determined by the colorimetric enzymatic test ACS-ACOD method using a commercial
150 kit (Wako Chemicals, Neuss, Germany). Haptoglobin was determined colorimetrically by the
151 hemoglobin binding method using a commercial haptoglobin assay (Assay Phase Range,
152 Tridelta Development, Maynooth, Ireland) and an Olympus AU400 analyzer (Olympus
153 Europa, Hamburg, Germany).

154 At d 25, blood samples (approximately 0.3 mL) were collected by insulin syringes (1 mL;
155 BD Micro-Fine, BD Medical-Diabetes Care, Franklin Lakes, NJ) at 0800 and at 1700 h and
156 immediately analyzed for major ions and metabolites. A single drop of blood was applied to
157 disposable cartridges containing biochemical and silicon chip technology (i-STAT EC8+,
158 Abbott Point of Care, Princeton, NJ). Then, the cartridge was inserted into an i-STAT
159 handheld analyzer, and the results of glucose, urea, Cl, Na, K, total CO₂ concentration, anion
160 gap, hematocrit, hemoglobin, pH, partial pressure of CO₂, HCO₃⁻, and base excess were
161 obtained.

162 ***Digestibility Coefficients, and Water and N Balances.*** Feed orts were daily collected (d 31
163 to 35), weighed, and composted for analysis. Feces of each goat were daily collected and 10%
164 of fresh feces were dried at 60°C for 48 h. Then a composted sample for each goat was stored
165 at room temperature until analysis. Urine was collected in containers with 20 mL of H₂SO₄
166 (96%) and urine volume was daily measured (accuracy, ± 2 mL). Urine samples (5% of total
167 volume) were composted and stored at -25°C for N content analysis. Samples of urine
168 without H₂SO₄ were collected at 0800 and at 1700 h during the last 2 experimental days to
169 measure urine pH. Orts and feces samples were ground through a 1 mm stainless steel screen
170 and then analyzed for DM, CP, CF, ADF, NDF and ash, as previously indicated. Water
171 balance was also done during the digestibility period.

172 ***Corticosterone in Feces.*** Samples of fresh feces were collected on the last day of each
173 experimental period and stored at -25°C for corticosterone analysis. Fecal samples were first
174 lyophilized, then were extracted with methanol, and finally diluted 1:10 with the assay buffer
175 of the kit. Analyses were performed in the Clinical Biochemistry Service of the Veterinary
176 Faculty of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain) using the
177 commercially available ¹²⁵I RIA kit (Rats and Mice Corticosterone kit, ICN Pharmaceuticals,
178 Orangeburg, NY), as described by Morrow et al. (2002). Recovery of known amounts of
179 corticosterone added to the processed samples was 59.8%. The relationship between
180 theoretical and true values of corticosterone in goat feces was linear ($y = 0.9919x - 2.863$; $r^2 =$
181 0.997). The inter- and intra-assay coefficients of variation were 16.8 and 9.5%, respectively.

182

183 ***Statistical Analyses***

184 Data were analyzed by the PROC MIXED for repeated measurements of SAS version
185 9.1.3 (SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model contained the fixed effects of
186 the treatment (HS vs. TN), day and period; the random effect of the animal; the interactions

187 treatment × day and treatment × period; and the residual error. The model took into account
188 the possible carryover effects of previous HS periods through the treatment × period
189 interaction. Data of performances (i.e., intake, water, milk yield) and physiological indicators
190 (i.e., rectal temperature and respiratory rate) were analyzed on daily basis.

191 For blood parameters measured at 0800 and 1700, the model included the effects of
192 treatment, sampling hour and period; and the interaction treatment × period and treatment ×
193 hour. Data on digestibility and nutrient balance were analyzed using PROC GLM of SAS.
194 The model contained the effect of treatment and period; the interaction treatment × period;
195 and the residual error.

196 Data were tested for the normality of distribution, and a logarithmic transformation (log₁₀)
197 was applied to haptoglobin concentration in blood. Differences between least squares means
198 were determined with the PDIFF test of SAS. Significance was declared at $P < 0.05$ unless
199 otherwise indicated.

200

201 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

202 ***Rectal Temperature and Respiration Rate***

203 Rectal temperatures and respiration rates increased from 0800 to 1700 h in both goat
204 groups, but were greater in HS than in TN goats at all time points (Figure 1 A and B; $P <$
205 0.001). The increased rectal temperatures and respiration rates in TN goats from 0800 to 1700
206 h were in accordance with the increment of ambient temperature throughout the day (15 to
207 20°C). Comparing the HS goats at 0800 h (after being exposed to 30.5°C during the night;
208 $\text{THI} = 77$) with TN goats at 1700 h ($\text{THI} = 65$), we observed similar rectal temperatures
209 ($+0.04^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P = 0.390$) but greater respiration rates ($+13$ breaths/min; $P < 0.01$), indicating that
210 HS goats were under heat stress throughout the day, but to a lower extent during the night.
211 Reference respiratory rate for adult goats ranges between 15 and 30 breaths/min according to

212 Pugh and Baird (2012), but it was greater in our TN goats at 1700 h probably because of
213 breed and physiological state differences. Maximum rectal temperature difference (+0.70°C;
214 $P < 0.001$) between HS and TN goats occurred at 1200 h, whereas the largest difference in
215 respiration rate (+65 breaths/min; $P < 0.001$) occurred at 1700 h. Increased respiration rate
216 under HS conditions is a known mechanism for dissipating heat load by evaporation. Rectal
217 temperature and respiration rate values peaked in HS goats during the first week and then
218 gradually decreased, which indicates a partial adaptation to the HS conditions.

219

220 ***Feed Intake***

221 On average, DMI decreased by 21% throughout the 35-d experimental period but showed a
222 marked effect of time elapsed after the start of the HS treatment (Figure 2; $P < 0.001$). Feed
223 intake under HS conditions gradually decreased during wk 1, partially recovered during wk 2
224 and 3, and remained constant thereafter (Figure 2). Heat stress caused a 27% reduction in
225 DMI from d 1 to 19 (1.47 ± 0.05 vs. 2.00 ± 0.06 kg/d; $P < 0.001$) and 14% from d 20 to 35
226 (1.75 ± 0.06 vs. 2.03 ± 0.06 kg/d; $P < 0.001$). The partial recovery of DMI from d 19 onwards
227 indicates the adaptation of goats to HS conditions. Previous studies comparing TN and HS
228 under chamber controlled conditions in dairy cows (Rhoads et al., 2009; Schwartz et al., 2009)
229 did not show such an adaptation.

230 Feed intake reduction due to HS has been previously reported in dairy goats (Sano et al.,
231 1985), ewes (Abdalla et al., 1993), and cows (Lough et al., 1990; Rhoads et al., 2009). Heat-
232 stressed animals decreased feed intake in an attempt to create less metabolic heat because the
233 heat increment of feeding, especially in ruminants, is an important source of heat production
234 (Kadzere et al., 2002). Moreover, the gut fill by water observed in the current study for HS
235 goats (see later) might also be related to the reduced DMI.

236 According to the lactational performances of our goats (Table 2) and the requirements
237 estimated according to INRA (2007), TN goats showed a greater feed intake (2.03 kg DM/d
238 or 4.6% of BW) than predicted (1.72 kg DM/d or 3.9% of BW), which allowed them to cover
239 their daily requirements (1.16 UFL and 102 g PDI) and to have positive energy and protein
240 balances (+0.29 Mcal EN_L and +80 g PDI). Moreover, TN goats gained 1.8 kg (+51 g/d)
241 during the experiment as it can be calculated from data shown in Table 2. On the other hand,
242 feed intake of HS goats was lower (1.60 kg DM/d or 3.7% of BW) than predicted (1.72 kg
243 DM/d or 3.9% of BW). If we also take into account a 30% increase in maintenance
244 requirements because of HS as indicated by NRC (2007), the energy intake would not be
245 enough to cover the daily requirements and resulted in an apparent BW loss of 1.5 kg (−41
246 g/d). The apparent BW changes in TN and HS goats included the inevitable variations in the
247 digestive tract content, which were unknown in our data.

248

249 ***Water Consumption and Water Balance***

250 Results of water consumption throughout the experiment and water balance measured from
251 d 30 to 35 are shown in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The HS goats had greater water
252 consumption compared to TN goats (+5.50 L/d; $P < 0.001$). The greatest values of water
253 intake were recorded during wk 1 when DMI was at its lowest value. However, water intake
254 values stabilized earlier than DMI in the HS goats (Figure 2) and remained greater ($P < 0.01$)
255 than in TN goats throughout the experiment. Increased water intake was mainly used by HS
256 goats for boosting heat loss by evaporation from the skin (sweating) and by respiration
257 (panting).

258 The total water evaporation calculated by subtracting water losses in milk, urine, and feces
259 from water input (water intake + water in food) was 3 times greater (Table 3) in HS goats than
260 TN goats (+2.23 L/d; $P < 0.01$). We were unable to distinguish between evaporation by

261 sweating and panting, but increased sweating rates have been reported in heat-stressed dairy
262 cows (Shwartz et al., 2009) and goats (Baker, 1989).

263

264 *Milk Yield*

265 Despite the reduced DMI, increased body temperature, and the known negative effect of
266 HS on milk production in dairy cows (West, 2003), milk yield and FCM did not vary between
267 HS and TN goats (Table 2 and Figure 2; $P > 0.05$). Brown et al. (1988) reported that the
268 exposure of dairy goats to constant conditions of 34°C and 25% relative humidity (THI = 79)
269 for 5 wk depressed milk yield in Alpine but not in Nubian goats.

270 Even when DMI was at its lowest value during the first wk, milk yield was not affected in
271 HS goats. During wk 1, HS goats may have been able to partially cover their lactation
272 requirements by body fat mobilization as indicated by the greater values of NEFA in plasma
273 at d 7 of heat stress (Figure 3). From d 14 to 28 blood NEFA levels were similar between
274 groups, but our late lactation HS goats were probably able to maintain milk yield because they
275 partially recovered DMI, tended to have greater digestibility (see later), and had lower
276 metabolic demands compared to early lactating goats. Milk yield response of dairy goats to
277 HS in early lactation needs further research.

278 Our results of NEFA concentrations from d 14 to 28 (but not at d 7) agreed with findings
279 obtained in dairy cows, where HS did not cause an increase in blood NEFA despite the
280 reduced feed intake (Rhoads et al., 2009; Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013). Thus, it seems HS
281 cows are more sensitive to insulin than TN, allowing a potent antilipolytic action of insulin
282 that will prevent body fat mobilization. Consequently, lactating HS cows fail to have
283 sufficient glucose for milk synthesis, and therefore milk yield was depressed. We did not
284 observe such a decrease in milk yield in our HS goats, probably because the glucose was
285 sufficient for the milk yield level at late lactation (see later).

286

287 ***Milk Composition***

288 Milk TS and fat contents did not vary ($P > 0.05$) between HS and TN goats (Table 2). In
289 short-term studies carried out using climate-controlled heat stress, milk fat was also not
290 affected in cows (Rhoads et al., 2009; Shwartz et al., 2009) despite the known negative effect
291 of summer on milk fat (Kadzere et al., 2002). This usual decrease in milk fat content of heat-
292 stressed dairy cows during summer might be related to a reduction in forage intake, which
293 could decrease the forage to concentrate ratio in the diet. In the current study, concentrate
294 amount was adjusted according to the forage intake in HS goats to maintain a constant forage
295 to concentrate ratio throughout the experiment and similar to that of TN goats.

296 With the exception of milk NPN, content of protein and protein fractions in milk (true
297 protein, CN, and whey protein) were reduced by heat stress (Table 2). Nevertheless, CN to
298 protein ratio was not affected. Similarly, dairy cows under controlled conditions of HS
299 decreased their milk protein content (Rhoads et al., 2009; Shwartz et al., 2009). Decreased
300 protein intake and increased sweat secretion that contains protein and urea (Joshi et al., 1968)
301 might have limited the availability of AA for milk protein synthesis. Moreover, the decrease
302 in milk protein content under HS may be due to a lowered microbial protein synthesis in the
303 rumen because of changes in rumen environment (dilution or clearance of soluble substances)
304 by the high water intake. Huber et al. (1994) indicated that under decreased feed intake
305 conditions, increasing the percentage of rumen undegradable protein and supplementing with
306 lysine increased milk protein content under hot conditions in dairy cows. On the other hand,
307 Bernabucci et al. (2002) suggested that decreased mammary synthesis of milk protein (rather
308 than the reduction in AA intake) is the reason for the low milk protein during the hot season
309 in dairy cows.

310

311 *Digestibility and Nitrogen Balance*

312 Goats under HS showed numerically greater values of digestibility and tended to have
313 greater ADF digestibility than TN (+3.1 points; $P < 0.10$), as shown in Table 4. To our
314 knowledge, no data are available comparing digestibility under TN and HS ambient
315 conditions in lactating dairy goats. Our results agree with those of previous research carried
316 out under climatic chamber conditions with male goats (Hirayama et al., 2004), dairy cows
317 (McDowell et al., 1969) and heifers (Bernabucci et al., 1999). The increased digestibility in
318 the HS treatments in the aforementioned studies might be partially due to the reduction of
319 DMI as also observed for HS goats in our results (Table 2). Another reason for the enhanced
320 digestibility under HS conditions could be a depressed passage rate of the solid phase of
321 digesta as reported by Bernabucci et al. (1999). On the other hand, a greater rate of passage of
322 the liquid phase of the digesta may be expected as a consequence of the dramatic increase in
323 water intake. This could have an impact on the availability of rumen soluble fermentable
324 compounds, although this statement needs experimental confirmation. The tendencies
325 observed for an increased digestibility of nutrients (i.e., DM, OM and ADF; Table 4) in the
326 HS goats might have compensated the reduction in DMI, and could partially explain the lack
327 of effects of HS on milk yield in our results.

328 Although HS goats had lower N intake (Table 4), as a consequence of the DMI reduction,
329 they experienced lower N losses in feces and urine, which resulted in similar daily N retention
330 to TN goats (13.9 ± 1.0 g/d on average). Despite the similar N retention, milk protein content
331 was lower in HS than in TN goats, indicating that ingested N would have been directed to
332 another metabolic functions rather than milk protein synthesis in HS goats. It is possible that a
333 portion of N intake was lost in sweat in the form of urea as previously proposed by Joshi et al.
334 (1968). Moreover, the possibility of a lower supply of essential AA for milk protein synthesis
335 could not be excluded.

336 Treatment by period interactions were detected for DM and CP digestibilities, and for fecal
337 excretion and apparent absorption of N (Table 4). These significant interactions could indicate
338 some carryover effect when HS goats went to the TN treatment in the second period.
339 However, this seems unlikely in our case as these interactions might result from the effect of
340 period on DMI ($P < 0.01$; Table 2), where the DMI reduction in HS goats was more
341 pronounced during period 2 compared to period 1 (data not shown).

342

343 ***Blood indicators and Urinary pH***

344 Heat stress had no effect on blood glucose, urea, hematocrit and hemoglobin
345 concentrations (Table 5; $P > 0.05$). A tendency in the treatment \times hour interaction was
346 detected for blood glucose ($P < 0.10$). At 0800 h, HS goats showed lower glucose
347 concentration than TN goats ($P < 0.05$), while concentration at 1700 h increased ($P < 0.001$)
348 and was similar to that of TN goats. It must be stressed that the morning blood samples were
349 taken 1 h before offering the diet, whereas the afternoon sampling was done 1 h after
350 distribution of the second portion of concentrate, which may have contributed to the similar
351 blood glucose levels between groups at 1700 h.

352 Blood pH is regulated by a complex system of buffers that continuously work to maintain
353 it slightly basic in a range of 7.35 to 7.45 in most mammals (Constable, 1999). Measured
354 blood pH was similar at 0800 in TN and HS goats, but slightly decreased at 1700 h ($P < 0.05$)
355 in the TN goats. Despite the importance of blood pH for understanding the mechanism of
356 respiratory evaporative heat loss, changes observed in our goats were marginally relevant and
357 varied within the normal range in both TN and HS groups.

358 Values of total CO_2 , pCO_2 , HCO_3^- , and base excess were lower in HS compared to TN
359 goats (Table 5; $P < 0.01$). The decreased pCO_2 and HCO_3^- under heat stress conditions agree
360 with the results reported in dairy cows by Schneider et al. (1988). The greater respiration rate

361 observed in panting HS goats contributed to a greater loss of CO₂, lowering the carbonic acid
362 content of the blood. As a consequence, HCO₃⁻ was transferred from blood to urine by the
363 kidney for maintaining blood pH constant. Heat stress had no effect on blood Na and K
364 concentrations in accordance with results previously reported in HS dairy cows (Schneider et
365 al., 1988). On the other hand, Cl concentration was greater, at both time points, in HS than in
366 TN goats (Table 5; *P* < 0.05). Calamari et al. (2007) reported an inverse relationship between
367 blood HCO₃⁻ and Cl in dairy cows under TN and HS conditions. Due to the greater Cl
368 concentrations of the HS goats, they also have greater anion gap values, compared to TN
369 goats (Table 5; *P* < 0.05). It was expected that the increased HCO₃⁻ secretion in the urine of
370 HS goats should raise the urine pH, but we observed the opposite as urine pH of HS goats
371 tended (*P* = 0.108) to be lower than TN goats. We speculated that HS goats were able to
372 increase their renal excretion of H⁺, which resulted in a partial re-absorption of HCO₃⁻ into
373 the blood as previously observed by Masero and Siegel (1977). In fact, the decrease in pCO₂
374 at 1700 h due to HS was more marked (-20%) than the decrease in HCO₃⁻ (-12%). The
375 secretion of HCO₃⁻ in urine and its re-absorption suggests a large requirement and turnover of
376 body bicarbonate to maintain blood pH during heat stress.

377

378 ***Haptoglobin Concentration in Blood***

379 Haptoglobin, an acute phase protein linked to metabolic stress, concentration in blood
380 plasma was greater in HS than TN at d 7 (*P* < 0.05), when effects of HS were more marked,
381 but differences between treatment groups disappeared at d 28 (Figure 4; *P* > 0.05). Ametaj et
382 al. (2005) indicated an association between increased serum haptoglobin concentration and
383 hepatic lipidosis in periparturient dairy cows. Hiss et al. (2009) found that elevated
384 haptoglobin concentrations in milk of dairy cows were associated with high NEFA values in
385 early lactation. This relationship was also observed in our HS goats.

386 It seems that HS goats at d 7 responded by increased circulating haptoglobin when they
387 were metabolically challenged as evidenced by reduced feed intake (Figure 2) and greater
388 NEFA concentrations (Figure 3). However, when goats were more adapted to heat stress
389 conditions (i.e. d 28), haptoglobin levels returned to values similar to TN goats.

390

391 *Corticosterone in Feces*

392 Fecal corticosterone has been used to evaluate stress in cows (Morrow et al., 2002). This
393 approach is based on the fact that glucocorticoids are secreted by the adrenal gland after the
394 activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis by a stressor. Circulating glucocorticoids
395 are metabolized (conjugated) in the liver and excreted via the urine and feces.

396 Corticosterone concentrations in feces did not vary between TN and HS goats and
397 averaged 4.28 ± 0.55 ng/g DM. Similarly, HS did not increase plasma cortisol concentration
398 in cows (El-Nouty et al., 1978) and goats (Olsson and Dahlborn, 1989). Nevertheless, it
399 should be stressed that fecal samples were collected at d 35, and it is possible that differences
400 between TN and HS goats would have been detected if fecal corticosterone was measured
401 earlier (i.e. at d 7 when HS goats were suffering greater metabolic stress).

402

403

CONCLUSIONS

404 Despite the reduction observed in feed intake of heat-stressed goats, they produced similar
405 milk yield to goats under thermal neutral conditions at late lactation. However, milk protein
406 content decreased in the heat-stressed goats with no change in milk fat content. Heat-stressed
407 goats had similar N retention to goats under thermal neutral conditions, indicating that the
408 ingested N might have been directed to another metabolic functions rather than milk protein
409 synthesis.

410 Further studies are needed to test the heat stress effects during early lactation and to clarify
411 whether reduced milk protein content is related to a nutrient limiting factor or reduced
412 mammary protein synthesis as well as to evaluate the effects on coagulation properties of the
413 milk.

414

415

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509 **Table 1.** Chemical composition and nutritive value (DM basis) of the ration ingredients used
 510 for dairy goats

Item	Fescue hay	Alfalfa pellets	Concentrate
Component, %			
DM	89.99	93.04	90.30
OM	89.70	86.50	88.60
CP	10.60	12.60	17.90
NDF	48.10	44.90	12.60
ADF	23.30	27.00	6.19
Nutritive value ¹			
UEm/kg ²	1.57	-	-
UFL/kg ³	0.57	0.68	1.17
NE _L , Mcal/kg	0.97	1.16	1.99
PDIE ⁴ , g/kg	66	83	129
PDIN ⁵ , g/kg	57	95	153
PDIA ⁶ , g/kg	24	47	79
Ca, g/kg	3.5	16.5	18.8
P, g/kg	2.5	2.5	9.1

511 ¹Calculated according to INRA (2007).

512 ²Fill units for sheep (1 UEm = 1 kg DM reference grass).

513 ³Feed units for lactation (1 UFL = 1.7 Mcal EN_L).

514 ⁴Protein digested in the small intestine supplied by microbial protein from rumen-fermented
 515 organic matter.

516 ⁵Protein digested in the small Intestine supplied by microbial protein from rumen-degraded
 517 protein.

518 ⁶Protein digested in the small Intestine supplied by rumen-undegraded dietary protein

519

520 **Table 2.** Lactational performances of Murciano-Granadina dairy goats under thermal neutral
 521 (TN, n = 8) and heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions at late lactation (values are least squares
 522 means and SE of the difference)

Item	Treatment			Effect (<i>P</i> <)		
	TN	HS	SED	Treatment	Period	T × P ³
Initial BW, Kg	43.6	44.1	1.3	0.720	0.576	0.832
Final BW, Kg	45.4	42.6	2.6	0.034	0.687	0.047
DMI, kg/d	2.03	1.60	0.08	0.001	0.010	0.152
Water consumption, L/d	5.5	11.1	1.20	0.001	0.322	0.468
Milk yield, L/d	1.24	1.21	0.02	0.198	0.001	0.674
FCM 3.5%, L/d ¹	1.38	1.35	0.07	0.529	0.004	0.226
Milk composition, %						
Total solids	12.89	12.41	0.29	0.259	0.625	0.734
Fat	4.21	4.22	0.19	0.961	0.898	0.124
Protein	3.84	3.36	0.15	0.030	0.793	0.986
True protein	3.62	3.12	0.14	0.022	0.977	0.965
Casein	3.21	2.84	0.12	0.034	0.179	0.709
Casein, % protein	84.1	84.9	0.64	0.200	0.001	0.091
Whey protein	0.63	0.53	0.04	0.029	0.001	0.332
NPN	0.22	0.24	0.01	0.155	0.001	0.797
Fat yield, g/d	52	51	2.9	0.678	0.021	0.210
Protein yield, g/d	48	40	1.8	0.001	0.220	0.183
NEFA, mmol/L plasma ²	0.192	0.137	0.031	0.081	0.673	0.335

523 ¹Fat corrected milk at 3.5%; FCM = L × [0.432 + 0.162 × (fat %)], being L liters of milk
 524 yield.

525 ²Average values of blood samples collected weekly from d 0 to d 35.

526 ³Interaction Treatment × Period.

527

528 **Table 3.** Water input and water losses of dairy goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 8) and
 529 heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions at late lactation (values are least squares means and SE of
 530 the difference).

Item	Treatment			Effect (<i>P</i> <)		
	TN	HS	SED	Treatment	Period	T × P ³
Water intake, mL ¹	5,504	9,728	1,863	0.035	0.859	0.638
Water in food, mL	143	127	7	0.034	0.010	0.083
Water in milk, mL ¹	969	1,004	62	0.547	0.157	0.293
Urine volume, mL ¹	2,143	4,757	1,737	0.410	0.993	0.796
Water in feces, mL	1,426	825	144	0.002	0.326	0.178
Evaporation water, mL ^{1,2}	1,074	3,304	1,430	0.007	0.442	0.476

531 ¹*P* values extracted after log transformation because of the non normal distribution of data.

532 ²Calculated by the difference between water input (water intake + water in food) and water
 533 losses in milk, urine, and feces without taking into account the water produced metabolically.

534 ³Interaction Treatment × Period.

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Table 4. Digestibility coefficients and nitrogen balance of dairy goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 8) and heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions at late lactation (values are least squares means and SE of the difference).

Item	Treatment			Effect (<i>P</i> <)		
	TN	HS	SED	Treatment	Period	T × P ¹
Digestibility, %						
DM	56.6	58.8	2.3	0.121	0.567	0.047
OM	58.8	61.2	1.4	0.109	0.408	0.058
CP	70.5	72.1	1.5	0.306	0.723	0.021
NDF	36.0	38.8	1.9	0.157	0.985	0.765
ADF	35.1	38.2	1.7	0.094	0.143	0.600
N balance						
Intake, g/d	48.4	42.1	0.8	0.001	0.012	0.059
Fecal excretion, g/d	14.3	11.8	0.8	0.010	0.351	0.017
Urinary excretion, g/d	20.3	16.4	1.3	0.012	0.962	0.268
Apparent absorption, %	70.5	72.1	1.5	0.306	0.725	0.021
Retention, g/d	13.9	13.9	1.0	0.950	0.162	0.057

541 ¹Interaction Treatment × Period.

542 **Table 5.** Metabolic and acid-base balance indicators of dairy goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 8) and heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions at
 543 different daily hours at late lactation (values are least squares means and SEM)

Item	TN		HS		SEM	Effect (<i>P</i> <)		
	0800 h ¹	1700 h ²	0800 h ³	1700 h ³		Treatment	Hour	T × H ⁴
Glucose, g/L	3.21	3.41	3.04	3.44	0.05	0.197	0.001	0.057
Urea, mg/dL	40.4	30.0	36.5	28.3	2.5	0.331	0.001	0.498
Na, mmol/L	139.5	140.4	142.3	141.0	1.2	0.161	0.881	0.403
K, mmol/L	3.83	4.16	3.70	4.25	0.10	0.793	0.003	0.399
Cl, mmol/L	105.0	108.9	108.3	110.4	0.9	0.031	0.004	0.324
Hematocrit, %PCV ⁵	18.63	17.75	18.25	16.63	0.63	0.372	0.003	0.296
Hemoglobin, mmol/L ⁶	6.33	6.03	6.23	5.64	0.21	0.363	0.002	0.187
pH	7.42	7.38	7.42	7.42	0.01	0.156	0.142	0.056
Total CO ₂ , mmol/L ⁶	26.9	24.4	22.3	21.5	0.8	0.002	0.036	0.231
Anion gap, mmol/L ⁶	12.50	12.00	16.50	14.00	0.73	0.001	0.099	0.428
pCO ₂ , mm Hg	38.9	39.8	33.1	31.5	1.7	0.006	0.769	0.300
HCO ₃ ⁻ , mmol/L ⁶	25.71	23.41	21.29	20.51	0.83	0.003	0.041	0.283
Base excess ⁶	1.38	-1.75	-3.00	-4.00	0.87	0.005	0.019	0.193
Urine pH	9.09	8.94	8.91	8.85	0.08	0.108	0.215	0.559

544 ¹Before changing from night (30.5°C and 40% humidity, THI = 77) to day (37°C and 40% humidity, THI = 85) conditions.

545 ²During the day (37°C and 40% humidity, THI = 85) conditions.

546 ³Indoors daily variation from 15 (night) to 20°C (day) at 40% relative humidity (THI = 59 to 65).

547 ⁴Treatment × hour interaction.

548 ⁵Packed cell volume.

549 ⁶Calculated values by the i-STAT device software.

550 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

551 **Figure 1.** Rectal temperature (a) and respiratory rate (b) at different hours during the day (0800,
552 1200, and 1700 h) in dairy goats under thermal neutral (TN, dashed lines, n = 8) or heat stress
553 (HS, solid lines, n = 8) conditions at late lactation.

554
555 **Figure 2.** Milk yield (○, ●), dry matter intake (Δ, ▲), and water consumption (□, ■) of dairy
556 goats under thermal neutral (○, Δ, □ with dashed lines; n = 8) or heat stress (●, ▲, ■ with solid
557 lines; n = 8) conditions at late lactation. The SEM values of milk yield, DM intake, and water
558 consumption are 0.05 L, 0.06 kg, and 1.14 L, respectively.

559
560 **Figure 3.** Plasma NEFA concentrations of dairy goats under thermal neutral (○, TN; n = 8) or
561 heat stress (●, HS; n = 8) conditions at late lactation. Values are means with SE indicated by
562 vertical bars (* indicates a difference at $P < 0.001$ between TN and HS treatments).

563
564 **Figure 4.** Haptoglobin concentrations in plasma of dairy goats under thermal neutral (□, TN; n =
565 8) or heat stress (■, HS; n = 8) conditions at late lactation. Values are means with SE indicated
566 by vertical bars. ^{a, b} Means with different letters differ ($P < 0.05$).

567 **Figure 1.**

568 a)

569 b)

570

571 **Figure 2.**

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574

575 **Figure 3.**

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578 **Figure 4.**

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